

Scope of Marketing for Schools in 21st Century in India By students at Universal Business School, Mumbai

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Abstract:- No longer are traditional schools given a market share of students or government funding depending on their location. Families that had few or no options in the past for their child's education today have a wide range of options. Thanks to the increasing number of options available to them in the form of charter schools and vouchers, families are no longer only sending their children to the school that was assigned to them based on their geographical location. Today's public-school employees must understand why, when, where, and how to market their institutions if they are to continue serving their communities in this evolving educational environment. If schools are to flourish in the modern world, they must adjust to a new working environment. Understanding how families pick schools for their children is crucial as the educational landscape evolves. Numerous books and essays have been produced to date arguing in favour of making it more necessary for schools to sell. We assert, however, that the literature's emphasis has fallen short of providing administrators with a fundamental knowledge of marketing theory. Instead, an excessive amount of attention is placed on communication methods and tactics, which causes educators to lack comprehension of the marketing process. This post will go through the fundamentals of marketing and how they may be applied in a public education system. In the context of the current competitive climate for educators, it focuses on the components of the marketing mix.

I. INTRODUCTION

Schools are very productive and play a significant part in our society. Unfortunately, it doesn't seem like many people are aware of this element of the story. Schools typically provide students with a richer experience that helps them prepare for life, including a wider range of subjects, more qualified teachers, guidance services, transportation, more extracurricular activities, social services, and special education services. This is in addition to the fact that schools are typically larger and offer these amenities. While understanding that the positive parts of the public school system are what make it stand out in the face of growing competition, administrators and teachers are still finding it challenging to spread the word about the good things taking place in their schools in the local community.

Delivering a strong story alone, however, is insufficient. The people who work in schools are not the helpless victims of the current educational institutions; rather, they are the valiant defenders of public education in the future. Despite the fact that this is not a skill set that has

traditionally or formally been taught, school administrators and teachers must learn to control their own destiny. Today's school employees must understand the why, when, where, and how to market their schools if they are to continue serving their communities in this evolving educational environment.

One of the most important parts of marketing a school—or any product, for that matter—is understanding the buyer. Understanding how families pick schools for their children is crucial as the educational landscape evolves. The process has evolved beyond just enrolling the child in the closest school and crossing your fingers. Today's families study schools in the same manner they do new appliances or vehicles before making a purchase. Sadly, many schools lack the resources necessary to assist families in making these choices. The schools are in for a wonderful chance. However, they will need to understand the reasons for telling people about what they do, be aware of how education is evolving, and work to create a detailed and coherent plan for effectively marketing their programme using both new and traditional media.

This post will go through the fundamentals of marketing and how they may be applied in a public education system. It talks about the marketing mix's elements within the framework of the competitive climate that today's educators work in.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A company, and educational institutions in particular, need effective leadership to reduce the waste of human resources. A leader should be able to get the most done with the least amount of resources if he or she is competent, experienced, and committed. A school or institution may have good rankings during one era but then perform poorly during another, it has been noted. Only the type of leadership in place at the time can be blamed for such quality swings. The leadership cannot function better without the active and professional support of the whole workforce of that business. The majority of the worried staff's backing is likewise focused on the effective leadership approach. The objective remains the same: the long-term development of the workforce and the company. The concerned leader may both positively and adversely reinforce the workers.

(Khan, 2020)

This anthropology is the study on how higher education affects people, organisations, and communities on both a micro and global level. With globalisation having a huge influence on both organised and unorganised markets

today, skill and education are the most important criteria in determining income. Major changes in higher education in both wealthy and developing nations have only been made possible by globalisation. Humans acquire information and skills on how to cope with a variety of challenges and situations both internally via training and experimentation with new ideas as well as externally through formal and informal interactions with the outside world. As a result of globalisation, the higher education system has both possibilities and problems. Knowledge displacement and interpretation jeopardise university autonomy and academic freedom. Although globalisation has surely advanced computer technology, communication, and education, it has not changed the lives of individuals who reside in underdeveloped countries, in poverty, or in rural areas.

(Sant, 1999)

Every public school now promotes marketing through presentations, conversations with students, parents, and teachers, as well as through internet connections, as was discussed in this essay. Because public school education satisfies the needs of a globalised society, public schools are preferred by people and are successful. These institutions respond promptly and appropriately when new circumstances arise. This article's goal is to investigate the reasons why marketing increases enrolment in public schools. To learn more about how these schools used their imaginative creativity and marketing ideas to construct the envisioned environment, more qualitative study is conducted. Public school marketing initiatives have increased as a result of parents' increasing concerns about their children's education and their consequent expenditure of a larger amount of their money on their education.

(Chander, 2000)

The study made the claim that social media is assisting in a global revolution of marketing strategies. Investigating the changes in the Indian education industry is crucial since it is now dominated by tech-savvy consumers who have fast access to information through both online and offline communication channels. This study aims to examine the relative weighting of various information sources in India's decision-making process for college and university admissions. The findings of a study of 255 freshmen admitted to first-year undergraduate programmes unequivocally demonstrate the expanding significance of online marketing tactics. The results demonstrate that offline marketing techniques are crucial and significant in the selection of students for colleges and universities.

(Sharma, 2013)

A. Hypothesis

As we write this paper, there are a few assumptions that we must keep in mind.

- Traditional marketing strategies now in use are ineffective in the twenty-first century.
- For two years, all schools were closed during the epidemic.
- Post-pandemic, India is today digitally sound.

B. Traditional Marketing Approach

The first thing we must realise about marketing in the modern world is that conventional methods and strategies no longer yield the same effects as they did five to ten years ago.

As we can see from our example, traditional advertising is not customised to your desired customer. The majority of traditional advertising employs the strategy of casting a wide net and "spraying and praying" based on the target population's demographics.

There has been traditional marketing for a very long time. It has become commonplace among people. Traditional techniques like signage, networking at events, cold calling, and referrals are utilised to harness the power of human interaction. This is a fantastic approach to finish a deal. Traditional marketing methods using physical canvas, paper, and other tangible materials provoke a response and create an impact. These may be acquired more easily than a physical shop or an online digital calling card.

On billboards, the use of printed or hand-painted designs on canvas is still rather common. Between roads and hallways, billboards have come a long way. This traditional marketing strategy makes use of less words and more images. Since a picture speaks a thousand words, compelling images are very effective in raising brand recognition. This form of advertising is generally known. Larger signs and billboards will never be ignored because of their extensive reach across social classes and geographic boundaries.

III. POST COVID-19 IMPACT IN EDUCATION SYSTEM

The collapse of the coronavirus has a significant and protracted effect on the world's educational system. The COVID-19-caused shutdown resulted in school closures for almost 250 million children in India. The education system faces a number of issues, including:

- **Educational disruption** - Students' personal and skill development was lost as a result of school closures.
- **Parent's dilemma over home schooling** - Children attend school to advance their education and overall development. However, in India, it might be difficult for parents to support learning at home due to their poor knowledge and resources.
- **Social isolation** - Pupils connect with one another at school, but with schools closing, it is difficult for students to learn and grow as people.
- **Non-Availability of resources to teachers and students** - A survey revealed that many geographic regions lack internet connectivity, which is a barrier to online learning.
- **Practical session difficulty**- The information that may be acquired via significant struggle.
- **A rise in the dropout rate** - The inability of many parents to fund their children's education as a result of job loss contributes to high school dropout rates.

IV. PARADIGM SHIFT OF EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Digital tools are increasingly being used in a variety of industries, including education, as a result of the statewide lockdown brought on by the coronavirus. To maintain the unbroken flow of knowledge, universities, schools, and institutions have shifted to e-learning. The epidemic has made it necessary for educational policymakers worldwide

to recognise the flaws in the present educational system. The demand for digital literacy, which might make a significant distinction between conventional and non-traditional teaching, is felt strongly around the world in order to understand the limitations of the modern educational system.

(Sharma, 2020)

Fig. 1

A. E-Learning Gateways

The shutdown has encouraged educational institutions' use of digital technologies so that they can collaborate more easily. In order to make online education delivery practical and worthwhile, now is the perfect time to experiment with and use new technology. Digital transformation has emerged as a new tool for educational institutions all around the nation without impairing students' ability to study.

Companies collaborated on NEAT, an AICTE project based on the PPP model to improve employability skills among students.

B. Government Initiatives

The Indian government and state governments have made a number of actions to help and benefit the students. SWAYAM online courses for instructors, UG/PG MOOCs for non-technology courses, e-PG Pathshala or e-content with modules on social science, the arts, the fine arts, natural and mathematical science, and the CEC-UGC YouTube channel are a few of the projects.

There have been other important projects launched, including Spoken Tutorial, Free and Open Source Software for Education (FOSSEE), e-Yantra, Google Classroom, and others.

- Vidwan, a database of specialists that shares knowledge with other professionals and potential partners.
- National Digital Library (NDL), a collection of learning materials with a single window feature, and Education Technology

C. Market Research Survey

We conducted a survey with instructors, senior school students, and former students to learn what marketing tactics may be used for successful marketing for schools. A survey is done to learn what customers desire.

Out of 100 responses that we have collected the above chart shows the following:

- Senior school students – 45%
- Ex-school students – 35%
- Teachers – 20%

Fig. 2

The above chart describes us the important factors people choose for a school. The result is below:

- 60.6% - Quality of overall education
- 22.2% - Quality teachers
- 12.1% - Co-curricular activities
- 5.1% - Infrastruture

Fig. 3

In order to present knowledge in a way that is helpful to the user, the aforementioned question was posed to study the most crucial aspect of selecting a school.

The person who posed the question above was requested to have an understanding of consumer psychology in order to determine the best marketing channel.

Here, we observe a shift away from conventional marketing techniques like word-of-mouth to modern ones like Instagram, Google, and websites.

“We may thus deduce from this study that a school should prioritise its website, Instagram, and Google results for successful marketing strategies.”

V. EFFECTIVE MARKETING METHODS

“The best marketing doesn’t feel like marketing” -Tom Fish Burne

The conversion of the most admissions possible for the academic year is the primary objective of marketing for educational institutions (schools). Therefore, campaigns, institutional partnerships, advertisements, and social media awareness will be the finest marketing strategies for a school.

A. Campaigning:

This would entail holding interschool tournaments and gathering leads for prospective students at other schools.

a) Process:

- Registration
- Holding
- Certification to participants

b) Competitions Examples:

- Quiz
- Extempore
- Drawing
- Sports

After the competition is over, we have a lead of prospective students that the university may turn into hot leads through target marketing and counselling.

B. Institutional Tie-Ups

This strategy works well for securing widespread admittance to any educational institutions. For a school, this entails searching the neighbourhood for mentoring organisations and unaffiliated small schools to connect with.

a) Potential Business Leads:

- Unaffiliated minor schools
- Disorganised coaching centres
- Teachers providing private tuitions
- Career counsellors

b) Process:

- Acquiring quality traffic for business
- Bargaining and establishing agreements for future admissions
- Pitching to their learners to increase conversions
- Academic discounts and scholarship advertising.

C. Advertisement

Displaying advertisements is effective when we're offering content rather than just deals and discounts. The digital marketing approach is seen as selling the values that a school upholds.

- a) Advertising Contents:
 - Showcasing the quality of teachers
 - Showcasing the quality of students
 - Student talent promotion
 - Students' testimonial
 - Events and exposure promotion
 - Co-curricular activities
 - Academic excellence promotion- past results
- b) Promotional Channels:
 - Google Ads (local store visit)
 - Facebook (Ads + FB groups + FB live)
 - Instagram ads (stories + reel)

D. Social Media

Maintaining a healthy social media presence is crucial in the modern world. The first thing an inquisitive customer will do after viewing an advertisement is search on social media for further information.

• Platforms:

- Youtube
- Instagram
- Facebook
- LinkedIn
- Whatsapp

We are able to leverage all of the aforementioned channels since India is now digitally sound and Indians' marketing preferences have evolved.

- **Youtube:** Schools can submit videos to YouTube to highlight their cocurricular activities and excellent curriculum, as well as to demonstrate the many teaching strategies they use. In addition to this, an institution may submit school tour videos on YouTube to showcase its facilities and record all of its minor events for increased visibility and channel engagement.
- **Instagram:** One of the most potent social media platforms of the twenty-first century, it. A school may use this platform to its advantage by posting high-quality content. Festival flyers, student praise postings, event reels, and promotional offers must all be included in school-related Instagram material. Instagram aims to reach a white audience between the ages of 16 and 40. In India, Instagram has become the primary marketing tool for businesses since the country became digital.
- **Facebook:** It is Instagram's primary application. Although many users are switching from Facebook to Instagram, Facebook still has a large user base that is made up mostly of people in the 35 –45year-old age range, which is the optimal age range for parents of schoolchildren. As a result, institutions cannot ignore Facebook. Because Facebook has organic groups and Facebook Lives to cover any events, marketing there is rather simple. These 2 Facebook features significantly increase organic reach. Facebook also includes a function called Facebook Jobs, which unintentionally promotes heavily and aids in teacher recruiting for schools.

- **LinkedIn:** It serves as the professionals' platform. Additionally, a school must be present on LinkedIn, where it must share information about the possibilities and exposure provided to instructors. This will encourage additional qualified instructors on LinkedIn to join the organisation. Additionally, a facility might publish its activities so that working professionals can get in touch with it directly.
- **Whatsapp:** When we have leads from prospective students' parents via campaigns like drawings, quizzes, and extempore competitions, it is the ideal communications tool to have on hand. WhatsApp may be used to nurture leads by forwarding pertinent school information, such as prospectuses, brief movies, website redirects, and promotional offers. The finest feature of WhatsApp is that users may use texts to clarify any misconception they may have.

VI. ANALYSIS

Initially, we made three assumptions for our research paper, however after doing a market survey, we can observe that there has been a change in the channels used for word of mouth, moving from Facebook to Instagram. In addition to this, we also presume that India is digitally sound, and now that we have reached this conclusion, we can say that India is critically sound because, in a survey of 100 responses, more than 40% of people suggested Instagram, which actually satisfies our assumption that India is digitally sound.

VII. CONCLUSION

The main aim behind conducting this research is to scrutinise the importance of online and offline marketing measures as a detailed source of school selection. Moreover, the study also intends to look at the variety and popularity preferences of different marketing channels that are available and successful in the Indian market, both in terms of popularity and usage, under the heading of digital marketing.

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